

Modular Automatic Test Equipment Design for On-Platform Diagnostics

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Abstract—A modular design for portable automatic test equipment used for on-platform diagnostics is described. The hardware and software architecture of the design are described in detail. The design comprises a core module that houses a processor and the primary instrumentation, measurement, and stimulus hardware of the test equipment. The design also includes an application module that provides platform-specific hardware capabilities and an interface to the system that is being tested. Modularity allows for the test equipment to be easily adapted for use on a wide variety of weapon systems and vehicles. The addition of optional wireless capability further enhances the portability and usability of the automatic test equipment when performing on-platform diagnostic tests and procedures. The test equipment is used in conjunction with a host computer that provides a user interface to the operator and directs the test equipment in interacting with the unit under test. The test equipment can also interact with or be directed by an Interactive Electronic Technical Manual running on the host computer. Communication between the test equipment and the host computer can be abstracted or encrypted as necessary, such that data transmissions are secure and accurate. When combined with vehicle health management systems, test program sets, and other automatic test equipment, the described design helps facilitate a two-level maintenance philosophy for military equipment and fleet vehicles.

Keywords—automatic test equipment, modular, wireless, on-platform, diagnostics, prognostics, maintenance, instrumentation, measurement, stimulus, switching, troubleshooting

I. INTRODUCTION

Within the realm of test, instrumentation, and measurement, test engineers often think of two main tools that help diagnose and test faulty line-replaceable units (LRUs): built-in test (BIT) and automatic test equipment (ATE). Through the help of modern technology, BIT and ATE have become increasingly valuable in a test environment, but they do not provide a complete diagnostic solution for on-platform maintenance activity, and instead, BIT and ATE may leave a gap in a system's overall maintenance philosophy if the users of that system wish to reduce no evidence of failure (NEOF) rates without requiring ATE to be used in operational environments.

This potential maintenance gap has resulted in the development of a variety of at-system test equipment over the past several decades. In most cases, however, these special test

tools are created with a specific platform in mind, and are only suitable for test on a single vehicle or family of vehicles. Because of this, individual components of specially designed test equipment are not often reused across platforms, and additional engineering effort is required each time a new vehicle or system presents a requirement for on-platform test equipment.

In order to fill a possible maintenance gap and reduce overall engineering costs in support of on-platform test equipment, the Automated Test Systems Division (ATSD) partnered with engineers from other divisions within the Armament Research, Development, and Engineering Center (ARDEC) to develop a piece of on-platform test equipment that would not only meet modern vehicle test requirements, but would also be adaptable for use on future platforms and LRUs. The result of this effort was the Wireless Acquisition Module (WAM): a low-cost, small-footprint, wireless data acquisition and signal stimulus device that employs a modular approach that allows for easy expansion or adaptation for new or changing test requirements across a wide range of systems. The WAM, in turn, reduces the need for the development of new platform-specific test equipment for new vehicles within a fleet or in situations in which a vehicle LRU changes during the fleet's lifecycle. Furthermore, this reduction in engineering effort can result in reduced system sustainment and lifecycle costs as well.

II. NEED FOR ON-PLATFORM TEST EQUIPMENT

Many military, aerospace, and fleet vehicles have a planned life expectancy of more than twenty years. In order to meet this goal, these vehicles must be properly maintained throughout their lifecycles. Recently, organizations responsible for managing large fleets of vehicles, including the United States Army, have transitioned to a two-level maintenance system. The two levels utilized by this type of system are typically referred to as "field maintenance" and "sustainment maintenance." Field maintenance is the maintenance activity that occurs "in the field" or on the platform being maintained, while sustainment maintenance usually occurs outside the operational environment or within a depot. [1]

In support of field maintenance activity, most modern LRUs have some form of built-in-test (BIT). BIT allows an LRU to recognize and report fault conditions during operation. Although BIT has aided maintenance activity and increased user confidence in detecting fault conditions by properly

identifying faulty LRUs, BIT alone is still insufficient to be used as a full diagnostic solution because it cannot detect all fault conditions within a system. The simplest example of why this is true is that BIT cannot provide complete detection of open circuits within a damaged cable. Additionally, BIT hardware is also susceptible to failure when the LRU in which it resides is subjected to extreme operating or environmental conditions. [2] In the event of a BIT failure, the user may not receive any fault information from a damaged LRU and will either be unaware of the problem or will experience symptoms of a problem without any additional information as to the root cause of that issue. Due to these shortcomings, BIT alone is often insufficient to provide reliable and comprehensive on-platform diagnostic capability, and some form of intrusive testing is still required to provide a complete on-platform diagnostic solution in support of field maintenance activity.

During sustainment maintenance activity, ATE is used to diagnose specific failures within faulty LRUs. Typical ATE devices provide maintenance personnel with sophisticated measurement and stimulus capability. This capability is more than sufficient to diagnose the root cause of a faulty LRU, and is often used to diagnose faults down to the shop-replaceable unit (SRU) level in a depot environment. The downside to ATE, however, is that it is usually expensive and large, and therefore, it is not suitable for on-platform diagnostics. Although some users have utilized ATE in the field, this strategy often involves logistical challenges, such as transporting the ATE to the location of a damaged or immobile vehicle.

Because of the limitations imposed by both BIT and modern ATE, alternative solutions are often required to support field maintenance activity. In order to be most useful, these alternative solutions must encompass the benefits of ATE, but cannot pose the same logistical burden found when transporting ATE in a field or operating environment. The WAM attempts to fill this gap by providing support for on-platform intrusive testing and providing capabilities similar to those found on modern ATE, but at a reduced cost, footprint, and overall logistical burden.

III. HARDWARE ARCHITECTURE

The hardware of the WAM was designed to be used across multiple projects and systems which require on-platform diagnostics. To achieve this goal of supporting a wide variety of platforms, the hardware was designed to be modular so that new functionality could be easily and inexpensively added as technology advances or platform requirements change. The hardware design also makes use of optional wireless capability to allow for easier access to on-platform test locations, and to improve the overall user experience. Size, weight, and form were also considered when designing the WAM hardware to work within the constraints of platforms with tight physical constraints, poor lighting, or hard-to-access test points.

As a system, the WAM operates with a host computer that communicates to the WAM module, directs the WAM to perform tests, and receives test results back from the WAM. The WAM is responsible for performing tests and communicating test results back to the host computer, which

makes decisions or performs analysis based on these results. Under most circumstances, WAM interfaces to the LRU under test through a series of test cables and test adapters.

The WAM can be used with an optional wireless transceiver operating in accordance with the IEEE 802.15.4 protocol. When operating wirelessly, a transceiver device is connected to the host computer, and communicates via IEEE 802.15.4 to the WAM. All communication is encrypted and transmitted without context. In other words, rather than providing detailed data through the wireless interface, simple command execution requests and “PASS” or “FAIL” results are the only transmissions sent over the wireless network. If wireless communication is not desired, a simple Universal Serial Bus (USB) cable can be used to connect the WAM to the host computer instead.

The WAM unit itself is comprised of three modules: a communication module, a core module, and an application module. Each of these modules provides specific functionality, with the goal that each can be interchanged with future modules. Additional test cables and adapters can be used to provide an interface between the WAM and the UUT.

Fig. 1. The WAM

The communication module houses all the WAM components necessary for the WAM to communicate with the host computer as well as the power components. This includes an optional IEEE 802.15.4 transceiver, UARTs, as well as the WAM battery pack and charging circuitry. For users that do not desire wireless capability, the communication module can be built without the IEEE 802.15.4 transceiver and battery pack, resulting in a wired-only WAM.

The core module houses the WAM’s main processor. The WAM uses an ARM Cortex M4 processor. The processor includes 2 digital-to-analog (D/A) stimulus outputs, 2 analog-to-digital (A/D) measurement channels, digital inputs and outputs, 2 UARTs, 1 I2C bus, and an Ethernet interface. These capabilities are what make up the “core” functionality of the WAM, which can be expanded as necessary with the application module.

The final piece of the WAM is the application module, which provides platform-specific capabilities such as signal conditioning and switching. By providing platform-specific

capabilities in a separate module, the core module can be reused with different application modules and remain common across multiple platforms. Additionally, if a single platform has a large variety of test needs, two separate application modules can be used in support of that platform's overall diagnostic solution.

The WAM also can be used with two additional pieces of hardware: a self-test module, and a charging module. The self-test module allows a user to test the WAM prior to ensure that it is working properly prior to using the WAM to conduct on-platform tests. This capability enhances user confidence and also can be used as a preventative maintenance procedure. The charging module allows the WAM to be charged from an AC power source. Alternatively, the WAM can be charged via a USB connection, but charging from the AC power source results in a quicker charging process.

IV. SOFTWARE ARCHITECTURE

The software architecture followed a modular design pattern to support the modular nature of the hardware. The software design goal was to support any future modules easily and reduce the amount of firmware changes needed for those modules. This reduces development time and greatly reduces risk if firmware changes can be kept minimal.

The software is divided into two sections for the WAM: the firmware, which resides directly on the WAM processor, and the application level software, which resides on the host computer. The firmware is used to accept commands from the host computer and communicate with the low level I/O hardware on the WAM. The application level software is designed to display diagnostic troubleshooting instructions to the user and to communicate with the WAM in order to perform diagnostic tests.

Fig. 2. WAM software is broken into two configuration items, an application running on a host computer, and firmware running on the WAM core module.

In order to meet the software design goals, it was determined that all hardware configuration and functionality would be placed on the application side of the software and the firmware would simply accept a list of generic commands and understand how to communicate with common hardware chips and circuitry. This would allow the most flexibility in the hardware configuration of the WAM, since the majority of the development would be done on the application side rather than the firmware when creating a new application module.

The first application module developed for the WAM was for the M109A7 At-System project. Included in this module

were digital I/O, EEPROM, and cross point switch matrix chips. Instead of writing firmware to directly communicate with the chips on the application module, generic messages were created such as “digital in read”, “digital I/O set configuration”, and “EEPROM write” which the application software would send to the WAM. Along with these messages, parameters such as the I2C address and device type were transmitted. This architecture allows future application modules to use these chips at any I2C bus address the hardware calls for without needing to change any firmware to communication with the new application module.

The other piece of the configuration stored in the application software is the pin mapping. This configuration maps physical pins on the unit under test (UUT)'s connectors down to the physical I/O channels on the WAM. Diagnostic procedures loaded into the application software use this pin mapping to determine which I/O channel to use when taking a measurement or performing a stimulus on a UUT's connector/pin combination. Since the diagnostic procedures are not written with WAM hardware I/O channels coded in, the WAM hardware configuration can change without affecting diagnostic procedures that have already been developed and tested. This allows procedures to be written before WAM hardware is finalized, and allows new revisions of hardware to change channel locations with only minor changes necessary to pin mapping configuration.

The application level software manages the connection, disconnection, and communication with all WAM modules connected to the host computer. In order to allow for more complex diagnostic tests, the application software allows for the use of more than one connected WAM at a time. To accomplish this, tags are assigned to each WAM that is being used for a diagnostic test. If two WAMs are required to perform an end-to-end test of a cable, the software would supply two tags: “Cable Side A” and “Cable Side B” which could either be automatically assigned by the software or manually assigned by the user. Using these tags allows the user to know which WAM to connect at which location and allows the software to determine which WAM to communicate with.

In addition to interfacing with and storing WAM configuration data, the application level software is also responsible for interfacing with the diagnostic instructions displayed to the user. Depending on the configuration of the host computer, these diagnostic instructions might be within an Interactive Electronic Technical Manual (IETM) or might be within custom embedded software developed to run on the system under test.

V. APPLICATION OF THE WAM ON M109A7/M992A3

The first project to implement the WAM was the M109A7/M992A3 At-System Diagnostics Kit. The M109A6, which is the predecessor to the M109A7, was equipped with on-board diagnostic and prognostic capabilities, but these diagnostics are not sufficient to provide a full diagnostic solution on the M109A7. [3] This is because the M109A7 and M992A3 have many more electronic LRUs. Although most of these LRUs are equipped with some form of BIT, BIT alone is

not sufficient to provide a complete solution for on-platform diagnostics conducted as part of a field maintenance strategy. Due to the limitations of BIT on the M109A7/M992A3, the WAM was evaluated and ultimately selected as the piece of test equipment that would be used for that platform's field maintenance.

As part of the effort to evaluate the viability of using the WAM, the signals found on the M109A7/M992A3 were analyzed in great detail. After evaluating the signals within the system, and comparing them to the M109A7/M992A3 requirements, a diagnostic strategy was developed to reduce the number of test points in the system while still being able to test the complex signals that could not be tested with a simple multimeter or oscilloscope.

An application module was developed for M109A7/M992A3, which used three 16x16 cross-point switch matrix chips to route 48 different signal lines from the UUT to analog and digital I/O hardware in the WAM application and core module. A subset of these switched lines also include resistor-divider networks to support the testing of voltages up to 40V.

The application module contains a cable with a 60-pin military-style connector. This cable can then be connected to test adapters which allow the WAM to interface to 60 different test locations inside the M109A7/M992A3 family of vehicles. Two different types of test adapters are used during testing of the M109A7/M992A3: single-ended and in-line. Single-ended test adapters allow for the WAM to measure or provide stimulus in place of an LRU. In-line test adapters allow the WAM to observe communication and signals between two different LRUs. The choice of which type of measurement is used at each test location was made by M109A7/M992A3 diagnostic engineers, and was based on the type of testing desired at a specific location.

Fig. 3. WAM shown with single-ended test adapter

On the software side, there was a requirement to integrate the At-System diagnostics into the vehicle IETM, which used the EMS NG IETM Viewer. In order to interface the IETM with the WAM diagnostic hardware, the WAM application-level software was run as a background application, called the 'PDK App'. This application used the GDI interface in the EMS NG Viewer to display IETM instruction pages and wait for user input to perform measurement and stimulus on the system. A user controls the flow of diagnostic tests from Maintenance Support Device (MSD), which serves as the host computer for the M109A7/M992A3 diagnostics software.

Fig. 4. Software communication for the M109A7 WAM implementation

VI. FUTURE WORK

The modular approach discussed above allows for the WAM to be easily adapted for use with other systems. This approach also reduces the engineering burden, as there is no longer a need to develop new platform-specific test equipment for each vehicle or system requiring field maintenance support. This results in reduced overall logistics and sustainment costs, thereby reducing the total lifecycle cost of a system as well.

Although the current WAM design is optimized for the M109A7/M992A3 and the current WAM application module targeted this family of vehicles, the current application module's capabilities could likely be used in support of other platforms as well. ATSD has evaluated several of these platforms, and believes that the current application module could be used as-is in support of these systems. If, however, new requirements or user needs were identified, the M109A7/M992A3 application module could easily be exchanged with another application module with different or additional capabilities. For example, with relative ease application modules could be designed and integrated with the WAM to support audio and video signal generation, audio and video capture, testing of controller area network (CAN) bus interfaces, and other yet-to-be-identified interfaces. The only constraints on these future application modules would be total power consumption, and the ability to fit the desired capabilities within the current mechanical boundaries of the WAM enclosure.

VII. CONCLUSION

By taking a modular approach, the WAM offers an inexpensive and easily adaptable solution to on-platform diagnostics in a two-level maintenance scheme. Modeled after larger ATE and commercial switch matrices, the WAM can test a wide variety of signals or provide stimulus to a UUT.

The overall modular design and exposure of generic interfaces allows for future expansion if desired. The common hardware modules and software libraries will also help to reduce development cost and schedule for future platforms requiring on-platform diagnostics in support of field maintenance activity. Therefore, the WAM may be a viable option for users seeking a piece of portable test equipment to be used as part of a larger on-platform diagnostic solution.

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